

Examining nurses' theoretical knowledge, attitude and practice of Cardio-pulmonary resuscitation in hospitals and primary health care settings in South Sharqyia, Sultanate of Oman

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Abstract:

Background: nurses are usually the first witness of sudden cardiac arrest in hospital settings, guidelines recommend that cardiac arrest should be managed through immediate and timely performing of basic support followed by advanced life support interventions. Although, nurses are expected to be knowledgeable in handling emergency situations and hence proper handling of cardiac arrest patients. However, studies and anecdotal evidences showed that nurses demonstrated poor level of CPR knowledge.

Objectives: this study attempts to identify the level of knowledge (Basic life support BLS, Advanced life support ALS), attitude and practice of CPR among nurses in South Sharqyia governorate, Sultanate of Oman. Moreover, it evaluates the association between the knowledge score and the selected variables (age, gender, level of education, work place, and years of experience). This will help to review the effectiveness of current CPR training, thus set up recommendations for better CPR programs.

Method and settings: descriptive, cross sectional study among 282 nurses using self developed questionnaires. the participants were selected randomly .The questions are compromised of three parts, which assess knowledge in BLS and ALS based on recent American Heart Association AHA guidelines. In addition, this study investigates the attitude and practice of CPR. The study performed in multicenter all over South Sharqyia governorate in hospital and primary health care institutions.

Data analysis: using quantitative approach to present the data, using SPSS package version 25. Spearman's correlation coefficient will be used to measure the strength of relationship between the variables. P values of <0.05 is also used for statically significances.

Findings: the response rate is 97%, and the findings demonstrate insufficient level of knowledge among staff nurses regarding CPR.

Keywords:

Hospital settings, SPSS package, CPR programs, Examining nurses, resuscitation

Why taking Care on Mental Health for Women during Pregnancy and Postnatal Time? – The Important Connection to Mental Health of next Generation. Practical Considerations

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Abstract:

Introduction: Mental disorders such as pre- and postpartal depression and psychosis are important facts on which attention should be paid on. It is important to support mothers suffering on these disorders not only for their own positive coping, but especially for their attachment to their newborns. Especially if there have been problems during pregravid time, pregnancy and birth.

We know about the difficulties of mothers feeling not as good and competent mothers. Since there are a lot of social asserts a mother has to accept and represent.

All professionals working with mothers during pregnancy and after birth should be aware and focused on that topic to identify possible/potential psychic instabilities and be able to handle them.

This presentation will show the impact of mental stability and practical impulses, which will help to improve mental stability for mothers and their children. On the other side it will make it easier to identify postpartal mental difficulties.

Conclusion: We have to focus on mental instabilities and disorders into mental health to create a firm basis for the children, the next generation: Mental stability is the basis for a broad and entire development of children.

Keywords:

Awareness to pre- and postpartal disorders and how to handle them Importance of mental stability to establish most stable, secure and independent development of children Simple application examples

Effect of Two Educational Methods on Knowledge and Health Beliefs Regarding Prostate Cancer Screening

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Abstract:

Prostate cancer is a common health problem that in the majority of cases starts to develop at the age of 50 years, reaching its peak at 60–70 years of age. One way to decrease the burden of prostate cancer is early detection through screening. Aim: The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of two different of education methods on knowledge and health belief regarding prostate cancer screening. Design: experimental and comparative approach design was utilized. Setting; the study was conducted at different administration departments enter the cordon of Suez Canal University. Sample: A purposive sample of 240 of men over 50 years and accepted in participating in the study and divided into two groups randomly (a group education and multimedia education). Tools: Data were collected through two main tools; I-A self-administered questionnaire to assess socio demographic characteristic and knowledge regarding prostate cancer prevention, questionnaire to assess participates in prostate cancer screening. II- health belief model to assess change in health beliefs during baseline, first and second post-test. Results; During the study, group education has participated in prostate cancer screening more than multimedia group. The group education raised the susceptibility perception on prostate cancer screening and while decreasing the barrier perception. Conclusion: the group education had a significant difference in the knowledge and health beliefs for prostate cancer screening more than multimedia education. Recommendation: Dissemination of prostate cancer screening through multimedia education based on HBM among men over 50 years to prevent the risk of prostate cancer.

Keywords:

Prostate cancer screening, group education, multimedia education

Articulating the agenda to manage the increase in neonatal sepsis: The Experiences of healthcare providers at Mbuya Nehanda Maternity Hospital (MNMH) NICU in Harare, Zimbabwe

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Abstract:

Introduction :

Maternal and child health are high priorities for international development yet the annual mortality rate per 1 000 live births from neonatal sepsis and other neonatal infections in Zimbabwe has increased by 11.6% since 1990, an average of 0.5% a year (Murray,2016). Zimbabwe's neonatal mortality rate is 24 deaths per 1,000 live births (UNICEF,2015). Successful intervention to reduce neonatal sepsis could be through simple interventions compliance to infection prevention and control guidelines (Newton and Berkley,2009). The study sought to determine the prevalence of neonatal sepsis, establish the factors contributing to the increase in neonatal sepsis and evaluate the practices on IPC by healthcare providers in MNMH NICU

Methods:

A retrospective cohort study was conducted at MNMH NICU on 100 neonates who were admitted from June-August 2016. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze data.

Results:

- There were 22 incubators but only 10 were functional leaving two or three babies sharing an incubator
- Klebsiella was isolated from the mechanical ventilators.
- Hand swabs revealed presence of pseudomonas
- No filters for suction machines posing high risk of back flow of secretions.
- Shortage of resources such as soap, paper towels and disinfectants
- guidelines is key in prevention of cross infection and it was given as a key recommendation.
- Non-compliance to IPC guidelines by healthcare providers
- Sixty percent of the neonates died of neonatal sepsis.

Conclusion/Recommendation:

Presentation of findings to NICU staff and the hospital management team led to improvement of IPC practices. Strategies implemented included decongesting of the unit, improving availability of equipment and sundries and conducting refresher courses for healthcare providers. It is therefore concluded that adherence to IPC guidelines is key in prevention of cross infection and it was given as a key recommendation.

Keywords:

Neonatal sepsis, neonatal infections, neonatal mortality, prevalence, neonate

Nursing Theories: Foundation of Nursing Profession

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Abstract:

Theories are the foundation for all profession. It provides sets of concepts that make the basic knowledge of the specific discipline. Similarly nursing theories are the set of concepts and principles that define the scientific basis of nursing profession. These theories help to differentiate between nursing practice and medical practice. Nursing theories provides a medium to rationalize the care provided by the nurses. Moreover, it provides an identity to nurses that differentiate nursing practice from the medical practice. Nursing theories are considered as indicators of evidence based nursing practices; however, re-searchers claim that their application is missing from the practice area. Nurses are on the verge of implementing nursing theories. They are facing many challenges and barriers in terms of understanding concepts, clarification of defined concepts for the implication and also from the research point of view. Current literature is limited in terms of highlighting issues nurses face while implementation at the clinical area. More research is required to identify challenges and barriers especially in the Pakistani context.

Keywords:

Nursing education; Nursing Foundation; Nursing Theories; Nursing Pakistan

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The Effectiveness or Efficacy of Modified Nursing Interventions Classification (NIC) in Reducing the Severity of Depression among Patients with Myocardial Infarction

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Abstract:

Background: Post myocardial infarction depression is common and puts a negative effect on recovery. Modified Nursing interventions effectively reduce the frequency and severity of depression in such patients. Objective: The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Modified Nursing Interventions Classification (NIC) in reducing the severity of depression among patients with Myocardial Infarction. Methods: Sixty-eight stable patients with myocardial infarction (>1 month history) having mild to moderate depression in accordance to Patient Health Questionnaire-9 (PHQ-9) [with a score of 5 to 14] were enrolled. Patients were assorted into interventional and control group. Modified Nursing Intervention was offered in Interventional Group. The frequency and effectiveness of Modified Nursing Intervention among the groups were determined and compared. Results: Both moderate and mild level depression was decreased in Intervention Group as compare to Control Group. Baseline mean depression PHQ-9 score was 2.35 point statistically significantly higher in the Control Group than Interventional Group (<0.001). After three weeks intervention the mean depression PHQ-9 score was 4.76 points significantly lower in Intervention Group than Control Group (<0.001). Conclusion: Modified Nursing intervention is effective in reducing the frequency and severity of depression compared to routine care in patients with Myocardial infarction.

Keywords:

Modified Nursing Intervention Classification, Depression, Myocardial Infarction

Pearson Chi-square=7.391
P-value (2-tailed) = 0.0065.

Figure 1: Gender wise percent of patients in both groups

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Improvement of Quality of Antenatal Care (ANC) Service Provision at Public Health Facilities in Lao PDR: Perspectives and Experiences of Supply and Demand Sides

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Abstract:

Background: The maternal mortality rate in Lao PDR (Laos) is still the highest in Southeast Asia, at 197 per 100,000 live births. Antenatal care (ANC) could contribute to maternal and child mortality reduction. The quality of ANC service remains inadequate and little information is available on the quality of health education and counseling services of health providers in Laos. This study aims to gain insight into the perceptions of stakeholders on both supply and demand sides of public ANC services in Laos and evidence for recommendations to improve the quality of ANC services.

Methods: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with 50 participants from different stakeholder groups; on the demand side, couples with a currently pregnant woman and mothers with children under one year of age and a family member; and on the supply side, health providers, managers, policy makers of the Ministry of Health, and development partners. The interviews were voice recorded and transcribed verbatim for analysis by open and thematic coding, using the MAXQDA software program.

Results: All respondents reported that the number of pregnant women who visit ANC services has increased. However, an analysis of the supply side identified issues related to the quality of ANC that need to be improved in the areas of facilities, human resources, privacy and confidentiality, providers' behavior, attitudes, and ineffective communication skills when it comes to providing health education and counseling to pregnant women and their family members. The analysis of the demand side mainly emphasized the issues of providers' behavior, attitude, communication and unequal treatment, and the lack of privacy. Both sides also suggested solutions to the problems, such as training, effective materials, rewarding good role models, and building a feedback system.

Conclusion: The number of public ANC services has increased, but both supply and demand sides experienced challenges with the quality of ANC. All respondents proposed possible solutions to improve quality of ANC service in public health facilities in Laos.

Keywords:

Antenatal care (ANC), quality improvement, stakeholders' perspectives, supply and demand sides, Laos.

Associations among menopausal status, menopausal symptoms and depressive symptoms in midlife women

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Abstract:

Objectives: To determine the associations among menopausal status, menopausal symptoms and depressive symptoms in Chinese midlife women. **Methods:** A secondary analysis involved 3199 women aged 40-55 years was performed based on data from the Women's Health Needs Survey 2018 in Hunan Province, Central South of China. The depressive symptoms were determined using the 9-item Patient Health

Questionnaire. The menopausal symptoms were assessed using the Kupperman Menopausal Index. Demographic characteristics and menopausal status were measured using self-administered questionnaires.

Results: The prevalence of depressive symptoms was 19.3%. The three most common menopausal symptoms were insomnia (48.0%), fatigue (42.7%) and mood swing (39.8%). The increase in depressive symptoms was significantly associated with menopausal status and menopausal symptoms. After controlling for demographic variables, multivariate logistic regression showed perimenopause[odds ratio(OR)=1.14 , 95% confidence interval(95%CI) =(1.12-1.86)], postmenopause [OR =1.52, 95%CI=(1.09-2.11)] and four menopausal symptoms including mood swing[OR= 1.32, 95%CI=(1.03-1.70)], depressive mood[OR= 2.28, 95%CI=(1.79-2.91)], palpitations[OR= 1.37, 95%CI=(1.06-1.77)], urinary tract infection [OR= 1.49, 95%CI=(1.16-1.92)] were associated with depressive symptoms.

Conclusions: Independent of demographic variables, perimenopause and postmenopause and four menopausal symptoms (mood swing, depressive mood, palpitations, urinary tract infection) increase the risk of depressive symptoms.

Keywords:

Menopausal status; menopausal symptoms; depressive symptoms; midlife women; China; a secondary analysis

Effects of Music Interventions for Preoperative Anxiety in Surgical Patient: Meta-Analysis

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Abstract:

Purpose: The aim of this study was to examine the effect of music interventions for preoperative anxiety in surgical patient.

Methods: We searched the Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), MEDLINE, CINAHL EMBASE, and Korean electronic databases such as KMBASE, KOREAMED, RISS, KISS, and NANET (2000 to November 2018). In addition, the authors manually reviewed the reference lists of the identified studies extracted from the database searches. The risk of bias was assessed using the Cochrane’s Risk of Bias (RoB) tool for randomized studies and the Risk of Bias Assessment tool for Non-randomized studies (RoBANS). To estimate the effect size, a meta-analysis of the studies was performed using the R program (version 3.5.1).

Results: We included 12 trials. The twelve studies showing the effect of music intervention on anxiety were heterogeneous ($\chi^2=23.42$, $p=0.05$, $I^2=40\%$). The effect size was -0.77 (95% CI: -0.93 , -0.60) and statistically significant ($p < .001$). Most trials were assessed to be at high risk of bias because of lack of blinding. Blinding of outcome assessors is often impossible in psychosocial intervention.

Conclusion: This systematic review indicates that music intervention may have a beneficial effect on preoperative anxiety. Therefore, the findings of the study may provide an evidence to incorporate various music intervention into nursing practice to reduce preoperative anxiety.

Keywords:

Preoperative Period, Patients, Anxiety, Intervention Studies, Meta-analysis

Figure 1: Comparison outcome of music intervention for surgical patient

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Helping Patients Cope With Grief: Creating a Pathway for Nurses

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Abstract:

Introduction: In the past, nursing students learnt about anatomy and physiology of a system, dealt with an infected toe, a brain with infarcts, a heart with surgeries etc. but nowadays, students are learning about the wholeness of people, an adolescent coping with self-esteem and ego, a young adult grieving or feeling stigmatized with the diagnosis of cancer and its complications. This is the world of Oncology

Purpose: To evaluate the role of psychological domain in Oncology patients to evaluate the role of psychological domain in Oncology patients.

Methodology: Qualitative Design Study Setting: Aga Khan University and Medical College and Kiran Hospital–Karachi Pakistan
Sample size: 50 patients Data Collection: Assessment tool –Questionnaire.

Result: Expert nursing care is essential for patient care in end of life care. The Oncology nurse provides the type of care that allows patients and families to grow in the experience of palliative care.

Conclusion: The role of an oncology nurse in the care of dying includes imparting information and education related to the bereavement process, offering emotional support, extending communication with the bereaved family after death, enabling effective palliative care which focuses on spiritual, psychological, physical, and social aspects of the patient's life.

Keywords:

Neonatal Nursing, patient Health care, Nursing Informatics, Menopause, Nursing education, Nursing research

Knowledge and Health Beliefs about Breast Cancer Screening among Rural Palestinian Women in Bethlehem Governorate: a cross-sectional survey

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Abstract:

Breast cancer is the most frequent type of cancer among women and is diagnosed at advanced stages of the disease. This delay in diagnosis results in poor survival outcomes even though the incidence rates are less than 40 cases per 100,000 women (Ferlay, Shin, Bray, Forman, Mathers, & Parkin, 2010). In the Occupied Palestinian Territories (oPt), women are less likely to participate in breast cancer screening.

The aim of the study is to examine rural Palestinian women's level of knowledge about and beliefs toward breast cancer screening (BCS), and to test if there are differences in demographic variables (age, level of education, socioeconomic status, health insurance) between women who participated in mammography vs. those who did not participate in mammography.

Study design : This descriptive, cross-sectional study investigated the levels of knowledge and women's perceptions about breast cancer screening. A convenient sample was recruited from the mobile clinics that are provided by the Palestinian Medical Relief Society (PMRS) in rural area in Bethlehem Governorate. The participants were women between 40 – 70 years of age and did not have prior breast cancer.

Analysis: Descriptive and comparative statistics used to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics used to describe the sample, frequencies, percentages for categorical variables, and means for quantitative variables. T-tests and Chi-square statistical analyses for inferential statistics.

Findings: The research questions examined the relationship of selected factors with the dependent variable identified as women's self-reported participation in screening for breast cancer of women. There was only one statistically significant variable that resulted from this pilot study. The variable "perceived benefits of breast cancer screening" demonstrated a statistically significant difference between women who affirmatively reported participation in mammography screening compared with women who reported non-participation. Examination of social and cultural influences about breast cancer screening behaviors will help to expand knowledge about barriers to breast cancer screening among Palestinian women living in the Bethlehem Governorate.

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Keywords:

Menopausal status; menopausal symptoms; depressive symptoms; midlife women; China; a secondary analysis

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